

LULLABIES IN THE CONTEXT OF ASSAM

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Lullabies are the first genre of folklore that is encountered by a human being. Also termed as "Children Lore" or "Cradle Songs", lullabies form a significant genre in the oral tradition of any community because of its variety, quantity and presence in every society of the world.

The tradition and history of a community is embodied in these lore and passed on to the child either by the mother or the elder female figure of the household or by the nurse. They introduce the child to a world and a culture through symbolic terms and expressions. These symbolic lore help the child to create a picture of a world that is beautiful as well as full of mysteries to be unfolded. Lullabies also possess the main characteristic feature of all the folklore forms, i.e., a continuous process of change, modification and addition, because lullabies, in most of the cases, are extempore and context-dependant in nature. For example, the singer of the lullaby always tends to address the child with its name or gender, uses the current context of the household such as, 'mother is going to work', or 'father is coming home with gifts' etc. and so on.

The fact whether lullabies come under the broader area called Narratives or not still remains as an arguable area. A stable narrative pattern is virtually absent from the lullaby tradition. Therefore, lullabies cannot be classified on the basis of the definition of narratives. This paper tries to analyze the factors which make the lullabies the kind of lore they are, taking the context of and examples from Assam.

Lullabies in Assam: Lullabies are known by a variety of names in different parts of Assam. For example, they are known as 'Nisukoni Geet' (Nisukoni means, to lull), 'Dhai Naam' (Dhai refers to the nurse), 'Soli Bhurkoa Geet' in Nalbari district of Assam, 'Sawa Bhurka Geet' or 'Nindali Geet' in Goalpara district, 'Koh Nih Nam'

or 'Brinih Nihtom' among the Misings and so on. Similarity in tune, lyrics and subject is a notable feature of the lullabies among the Asomiya-speaking population and different neighboring tribes. This similarity can be attributed to their close proximity with one another and the similar socio-environmental contexts that they share.

In order to make a detailed study of the important factors related to the lullabies, we will have to locate the aspects which separate them from other narratives. These differing aspects may include the language and the technique used to render a lullaby, its motifs, functions, usage and the characters usually used.

The Language and Style: The narrator evokes the mood and message of the lullaby. The language and words used are evoked by the pure and extensive abundance of the imaginations of the narrator. Therefore, sometimes a lullaby goes on and on stringing together some unrelated persons, things or animals. For example, this very common lullaby in Asomiya households (translation also), goes on and on till at one point the mother expresses her dream to see her child as 'bormanuh' or a great man:

*Junbai ae, beji eta diya
Beji nu keloi
Muna xiboloi
Muna nu keloi
Dhon bhoraboloi
Dhon nu keloi
Hati kiniboloi
Hati nu keloi
Uthi phuriboloi...*

(Ae moon, give me a needle,
what for the needle?
to stitch a bag,

what for the bag?
to keep the money,
what for the money?
to buy an elephant,
what for the elephant?
to ride around.....)

There is very less or almost no connectivity between two adjacent words or two following lines. A reason for this may be that it is sung in a relaxing mood, the mind open for imaginations to pop up, remembering the exotic abundance of nature. One other reason may be to help the child create a world-picture of its own using and developing its imaginative skills. An *Asomiya nisukoni geet* may help here,

Panikauri, panikauri,
The king is calling,
I can't come, I can't come
My feet are cracking.
The one young brother that I have
Is again a dwarf?
Dances round and round
He is like a jack-fruit seed.

This lullaby actually makes no sense, although it amuses the child, creating an entertaining atmosphere.

The words used in these lullabies are taken from day-to-day lives of the rural folks, crisp, mixed with the essence and scent of the soil. A lullaby from Goalpara goes,

ou kumolia, khabole borhiya,
kotari agore lun ae,
bapa kumoliya, otike dh uniya,
gaate jilike xun ae.

In the simplest form of a lullaby, the narrator hums and repeats some monotonous yet soothing sounds. For example, a Bodo lullaby says,

Oi moon, come o come
Oi moon come,
If you can't come,
Give me a banana,
Oi moon, come o come
Oi moon come.

The narrator goes on humming the last two

lines until the child falls asleep.

The amiable tune and the rhythm create a rhythmic atmosphere, in which the child loses itself into a different world. A very popular lullaby of Assam goes,

rodali ae, rod de,
ali kati jali dim
borpira pari dim,
tate bohi bohi rod de.
rodalir makor tinidal suli
rodali palegoi birinar guri.

Techniques employed: 1. Lullabies are sung softly with extensive use of expressions repeated again and again till the voice trails off to a whisper, as the baby falls asleep. 2. The narrator makes some melodious sounds with frequent movements of the tongue such as 'hushh', 'ssh', 'la', 'oi oi' 'na na' etc. The use of these formula words is a technique employed very often. 3. The mother or the narrator uses her fingers too to lull the baby to sleep. These finger-plays include caressing, rocking the baby's back, etc. There is a Khasi lullaby where the mother uses the baby's fingers to lull it. The lullaby goes,

This one (finger) says give me rice, mother
This one (finger) says for whom is the rice
This one (finger) says
lets borrow some,
Run to the jungles Let's eat pumpkin leaves.

While singing this the mother takes the baby's fingers one by one, starting with the small finger and ending with the thumb, and lifts the thumb to the baby's mouth. These finger-plays are used to create a tickling effect too.

Motifs and Functions: Motif is considered as the structuring element of a lullaby. Therefore, motifs and functions are interrelated concepts in the case of lullabies. Some motifs can be noted down as mentioned below.

1. "Everyone's asleep, you sleep too".
2. Calling forth a soother. This depends on the singer's relation with the child.
3. To teach a lesson of civic behaviour for the future.
4. To scare.

The main function of lullabies is to make the child

forget pain or hunger or send him to a peaceful, dreamy lull. As against the harshness and pain of the reality, the child is drawn towards a rosy world which interests and amuses it. Lullabies are also meant to create an awe and respect for life as a miraculous process in the mind of the child.

The infant is considered as a transitional and incomplete being. This surely affects the function of lullabies. The main functions listed below can be realized through various motifs:

1. *Lulling the baby to sleep:*

This function is to be realized through the poetics and phonetics of lullabies.

2. *Protection:*

Traditionally, folks believe that infants are susceptible to evil powers. This belief affects the lullabies. Such lullabies create fear in the baby's mind and also suggest a way to counter it. Sometimes the element of *charm* and *magic* enters here too. The evil power may be a fox (usually the cunning, dangerous kind), or may be an imaginary figure, e.g. Kankhuwa (the one who eats ears). An Assamese lullaby says,

“xiyaali aye... nahibi rati
ture kaane kaati logame baati”

2. *Prognostic functions:*

The mother dreams to see her child as a wise and healthy person, who will be very successful in the future. The mother's rocking, washing, bathing, feeding or tending the baby etc. symbolize the healthy development of the child's organs. These acts are accompanied by lullabies through which the mother lets the child know about her dreams for it. An illiterate Karbi mother sings,

O my plump child,
Grow more and fast,
I will send you to *zirsang*
When you will be of age.

Zirsang is a place where Karbi children and youth are provided institutional education. A common lullaby sung by every Asomiya mother is,

Our little child will sleep,
He will grow palm trees in the garden,
The palms from the garden will ripe
Our little maina will eat them.

3. *Epistemological Function:*

This particular function falls under the motive to create a certain initial worldview for the child through time, space, family or kin, life and its ways etc. The concept of the parents and the familial life is being depicted very clearly in this lullaby of the Dimasa tribe of Assam.

Father did not take *Babai*,
Got tired to see him,
Did not take *Babai* on the lap,
Did not carry *Babai* on the back,
Mother will carry you,
Lovingly till you sleep.

The following lullaby from the lower part of Assam introduces the child to many a things and persons,

*Xoru xoru soka ae, amar dhan nakhabi,
Mamather dak jabi, mamather dhan khabi,
Ekpura dhan dim, dalot bohi khabi.
Dal-dul bhanggi toi, telither dak jabi,
Teli dibo tel-gamocha, mali dibo phul,
Burar putakor biya hoisi, kuni kubabu dhul?*

Characters: The characters in lullabies are mostly taken from day-to-day life, from nature and cosmos, from myths or they can be some divine characters. The characters commonly involved in the lullabies can be broadly divided into three major parts such as, soothers, helpers and harmers.

The role of the soother is normally played by the mother herself with her tender narrative technique, warmth and the comfortable atmosphere that she creates around her child. Otherwise some characters are invited from outside, some foreigners such as the moon, some imaginary deity of sleep and so on.

Harmer is a character whom the child is scared of, someone who had scared it in recent past, or can also be some character that the mother creates to scare the child. Harmers can be animals, ghosts, some imaginary person, or some real persons who scare the child a lot, mainly for their appearance. The notable thing is that, these characters never actually carry out the aggressive acts attributed to them, in the lullaby. The mother gives just a hint of a possible attack or harm. The harmer character is normally shooed away by the soother or by the child itself at the end of the lullaby.

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the lulling atmosphere for the child. All the other characters used in the lullabies except the soothers and the harmers are helpers.

Lullabies in the Written Tradition: Written lullabies exist parallel with the folk, oral lullabies. Oral lullabies perpetuate a tradition through themselves, whereas literary lullabies speak only through the author's voice. While written lullabies are self-contained, the oral ones go through and live by a process of transformation, modification, addition and time-relevant changes.

One very evident relationship between the two is that literary or written lullabies, in time, becomes oral and vice versa. Thus a folklorisation of the written lullabies is always on the process.

Conclusion: Lullabies are an established genre in the vast oral tradition of folklores. With their quantity and variety, lullabies are nowhere near becoming a dead

tradition. Its usage, of course, now-a-days has different levels and degrees because of the societal set-up of the time. No mother, at the present scenario, will want her child to become a 'bormanuh' who then will play the drum, as in the Assamese lullaby,

*Bormanuh hole ki hoi?
Godhulite godhulite doba kubai.*

In another lullaby, the mother aspires the child to stitch a bag for the red buffalo, so that he can sale to it the butcher in the market of Goalpara. These symbolize the aspirations of Assam of a particular time.

The agrarian life has resulted in the lullabies that were available to us in the last centuries. The times have changed, many cross-cultural connections have taken place and with them the dreams of the parents for the children, the needs and necessities for the child's future have also changed. Many new terms and ways of life have, therefore, been added to the lullabies.